

Gauteng Urban Surveys 1. Checklist of the spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Little is known about the diversity of invertebrates in urban areas in South Africa. This survey of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The results of sampling undertaken over a six-year period in Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in the Gauteng province, South Africa, is provided. A total of 103 species, 85 genera, from 31 families were recorded. Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and hand collecting. The most species-rich families were the Salticidae (17 spp.), Araneidae (12 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (11 spp.), while 19 families are represented by singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Four of the species are vulnerable and one is near threatened.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, diversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida, urban surveys

INTRODUCTION

This survey forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). The project was initiated in 2014 (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014). The green urban areas can be potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, promoting connectivity between species' meta-populations both within and outside towns and cities. Unfortunately, the evidence for these functions for spiders in Southern Africa is either anecdotal or completely lacking. The first report on spiders in urban areas was by Tucker (1920) on the spiders of Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, while Clark and Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanic garden in Pietermaritzburg, South Africa. More recently, surveys were undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden Bloemfontein, South Africa (Butler & Haddad 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013, 2018).

Gauteng is by far the smallest province, covering only 1.4% of South Africa. As part of SANSa, a total of 350 sites in Gauteng have already been sampled, represented by 6 800 records, 56 families and 641 species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This includes a total of 24 protected areas. Surveys in Gauteng urban areas include several reserves and botanical gardens: Serene Valley (Kelly *et al.*, 2014), Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014), Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014), as well as the Pretoria National Botanical Gardens (Kassimatis, 2008), Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991) and Irene grassland survey. Other surveys not in urban areas include surveys in agro ecosystems at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) Roodeplaat Campus (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976) and Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989; Engelbrecht, 2013).

This paper presents the first species list and information on the spider fauna of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve. Information on endemism and conservation status for each of the 102 species is provided.

METHOD

Study area: The Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (25° 46' 16.2516" S; 28° 17' 40.47" E) in Pretoria forms part of the Bronberg Conservation Area, which was declared in 1980. It is a 128-ha area in urban surroundings, boasting idyllic scenery, an abundance of birdlife and a series of nature trails and walks. The reserve transitions between *bankenveld* (grassland) and sour bushveld (acacia veld). The reserve also forms part of the 8-km Moreleta Spruit Nature Trail, while the perennial Moreleta Spruit flows through it, which is responsible for abundant grassland and rich vegetation.

Sampling methods and identification: The second author (PW) hand collected specimens, as well as using a sweepnet. He visited the reserve in 2013 (June), 2014 (February, April, September), 2015 (April), 2017 (November) and 2020 (February). Live spiders were sampled, photographed and then preserved in 70% ethanol. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Tables 1 & 3).

Endemicity value: The endemicity value for each species is provided (Table 3) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised: 6 = when Faerie Glen Nature Reserve is the type locality; 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE endemic to South Africa but known from two adjoining provinces; 3 = SAE South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining; 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons) or DD when there is a lack of distribution data. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 103 species in 85 genera and 31 families were sampled (Tables 1 & 3). Four species (Araneidae, Theridiidae, Mimetidae and Oxyopidae) could not be identified to species level as they were probably new or still immature. Unfortunately, some of them belong to large families that require comprehensive revision to determine the taxonomic status and identity of these taxa.

Family diversity: Of the 31 spider families collected from Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Tables 1 & 2), the Salticidae (17 spp.), Araneidae (12 spp.) and Thomisidae with (11 spp.) were the most species-rich.

Endemicity: Forty-eight species (46.6%) sampled at Faerie Glen Nature Reserve have a wide distribution throughout Africa (AE) while 17.5% are known from Southern Africa and only 23.2% are South African endemics.

Four species are Gauteng endemics: *Hortipes coccinatus* Bosse-laers & Jocqué, 2000 (Corinnidae); *Idiops pretoriae* (Pocock, 1898) (Idiopidae) and two members of the Stasimopidae: *Stasimopus hewitti* Engelbrecht and Prendini, 2012 and *S. robertsi* Hewitt, 1910.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Faerie Glen Nature Reserve with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	G	SPP.	FAMILIES	G	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	1	6
Araneidae	10	12	Palpimanidae	1	1
Bemmeridae	1	1	Philodromidae	3	3
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	1
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	3	3
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Salticidae	14	17
Deinopidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	6	7	Selenopidae	1	1
Hersiliidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	2
Idiopidae	3	3	Theridiidae	7	9
Linyphiidae	1	1	Thomisidae	8	11
Lycosidae	5	6	Trachelidae	2	2
Mimetidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Oecobiidae	1	1		85	103

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve

Conservation status	No. of spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	0	DD	0
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	4	NE	3.9
Least concern	94	LC	91.3
Vulnerable	4	VU	3.9
Near threatened	1	NT	0.9
Endemicity			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	9	LC	8.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	48	LC	46.6
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	18	LC	17.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	19	LC	18.4
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	1	VU	0.9
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	4	VU,NT	3.9
6 – Type locality	0		0

Stasimopus robertsi Photo Les Oates

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Figs 1–15. Spiders collected at the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve: 1. *Araneus apricus* (Araneidae). 2. *Neoscona subfusca* (Araneidae). 3. *Pararaneus cyrtoscapus* (Araneidae). 4. *Lipocrea longissima* (Araneidae). 5. *Hypsosinga holzapfelae* (Araneidae). 6. *Menneus camelus* (Deinopidae). 7. *Micaria beaufortia* (Gnaphosidae). 8. *Merenius alberti* (Corinnidae). 9. *Hortipes coccinatus* (Corinnidae). 10. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Cheiracanthiidae). 11. *Camillina cordifera* (Gnaphosidae). 12. *Pardosa crassipalpis* (Lycosidae). 13. *Hogna zuluana* (Lycosidae). 14. *Oxyopes bothai* (Oxyopidae). 15. *Oxyopes* sp. 3. Photo credits: Peter Webb

Figs 16-29. Spiders collected at the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve: 16. *Vidole sothoana* (Phyxelididae). 17. *Heliophanus debilis* (Salticidae). 18. *Pellenes bulawayoensis* (Salticidae). 19. *Pseudicius gracilis* (Salticidae). 20. *Natta horizontalis* (Salticidae). 21. *Afrocto martini* (Trachelidae). 22. *Enoplognatha molesta* (Theridiidae). 23. *Steatoda capensis* (Theridiidae). 24. *Ariadna bilineata* (Segestriidae). 25. *Scytodes caffra* (Scytodidae). 26. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pisauridae). 27. *Miagrammopes brevicaudus* (Uloboridae). 28. *Synema imitatrix* (Thomisidae). 29. *Thomisus blandus* (Thomisidae). 30. *Runcinia aethiops* (Thomisidae). Photo credits Peter Webb

TABLE 1: Spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS), global distribution and known sex F (female), M (male), B (both).

FAMILY, SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
FAMILY AMAUROBIIDAE				
<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY ARANEIDAE				
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hypsosinga holzapfelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zygiella</i> sp.		NE		
FAMILY BEMMERIDAE				
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY CLUBIONIDAE				
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY CORINNIDAE				
<i>Hortipes coccinatus</i> Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
FAMILY CYRTAUCHENIIDAE				
<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B
FAMILY DEINOPIIDAE				
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
FAMILY ERESIDAE				
<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY GNAPHOSIDAE				
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Micaria felix</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY HERSILIIDAE				
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY IDIOPIDAE				
<i>Galeosoma robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1916	4	VU	SAE	F
<i>Idiops pretoriae</i> (Pocock, 1898)	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B

FAMILY LINYPHIIDAE

<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C	B
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FAMILY LYCOSIDAE

<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Hogna lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1960)	3	LC	SAE	F
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<i>Hogna zuluana</i> Roewer, 1959	3	LC	SAE	F
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<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY MIMETIDAE

<i>Mimetus</i> sp.			NE	
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FAMILY OECOBIIDAE

<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	B
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FAMILY OXYOPIDAE

<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	F
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<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3			NE	
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<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	B
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<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY PALPIMANIDAE

<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	F
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FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE

<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	F
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<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY PHOLCIDAE

<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY PHYXELIDIDAE

<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY PISAURIDAE

<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Euprosthénopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY SALTICIDAE

<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE	B
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<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Heliophanus aberdarensis</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus lesserti</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY SALTICIDAE

<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesołowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesołowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Myrmarachne inflatipalpis</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE	M
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesołowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY SCYTODIDAE

<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
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FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE

<i>Ariadna bilineata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	F
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FAMILY SELENOPIDAE

<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE	F
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FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE

<i>Stasimopus hewitti</i> Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Stasimopus robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1910	5	NT	SAE	B

FAMILY THERIDIIDAE

<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Episinus marignaci</i> (Lessert, 1933)	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	B
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	B
<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Theridion sp. 2</i>		NE		
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	F

FAMILY THOMISIDAE

<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisops bullatus</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C	B
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	B

FAMILY TRACHELIDAE

<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY ULOBORIDAE

<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C	B

Endemicity (END): (6) Only known from the type locality, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve endemic; (5) endemic to Gauteng province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to Southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, Southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; GE, Gauteng endemic.